

Breeding methods — hybrid rice

Combining ability and heterosis of agronomic traits in indica PGMS lines and their hybrids

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In a two-line hybrid rice system, photo-period-sensitive, genic male sterile (PGMS) rices are used. Knowledge of the combining ability and heterosis of PGMS lines and their hybrids is needed for selecting good combiners for high vigor combinations.

We crossed indica PGMS lines W6154S, W6184S, W6417S, W7415S, and W6434S, and 6 test lines in a 5 × 6 mating pattern. Thirty F₁ hybrids, 6 testers, and 2 check combinations were planted at 25 × 17 cm, in a random design with three replications.

General combining ability (GCA) and specific combining ability (SCA) were analyzed for grain yield per plant and 10 other agronomic traits. GCA and SCA were significant for all traits, indicating that additive and nonadditive interactions were important (Table 1).

Variations due to SCA were greater than those due to GCA for grain yield per plant and fertile spikelets per panicle,

suggesting dominant gene action.

Variations due to GCA were greater than those due to SCA for other traits.

PGMS lines W6154S and W6184S were good general combiners for grain yield per plant (Table 2). Heterobeltiosis ranged from 246.8 to 2.0% for grain yield per plant. Combinations W6154S/Teqing 2 and W6184S/02428 yielded 3.2 and 12.8% more, respectively, than check Shan-you 63, the best three-line system combination. ■

Table 2. Estimates of SCA and GCA effects for yield per plant of PGMS lines and cross combinations.

Female parent	SCA of crosses with each given male parent						GCA ^{ab}	Variance of SCA
	Minghui 63	Teqing 2	02428	Qingsiai	Ce 64	Ce 49		
W6154S	0.659	6.759	7.384	-3.691	-03.744	-7.368	5.561*a	22.887
W6184S	0.591	1.714	13.626	-3.653	-6.399	-5.880	5.402*a	48.322
WG417S	-7.227	-2.520	-4.125	7.296	2.980	3.596	-2.007 b	29.216
W7415S	1.432	5.972	-14.364	-1.922	5.138	3.744	-3.328 b	50.389
W6434S	4.554	-11.926	-2.521	1.970	2.024	5.907	-5.628*b	35.180
GCA ^b	2.761	2.354	0.276	-1.465	-1.572	-2.355		
	a	ab	ab	b	b	c		
Variance of SCA	14.403	16.043	50.673	30.133	11.386	109.927	K ² _{fm} = 46.51	

^a* = Significantly different from zero at 5% level of probability. ^bDifferent letters show significant difference in GCA at 5% level of probability.

Table 1. Analysis of variance for combining ability for yield and yield components of PGMS lines.

Source ^b	MS and F test for agronomic characters										
	Yield/plant	Panicles/plant	Spikelets/panicle	Fertility (%)	Grains/panicle	1000-grain weight	Days to heading	Plant height	Tillering ability	Panicle length	Spikelet density
GCA1	481.0**	7.5*	1091.3**	1118.4**	3110.8**	71.7**	230.1**	31.7**	45.2	1.2	152.2**
GCA2	70.2*	26.8**	43172.3**	1813.6**	3377.2**	201.0**	1467.3**	1339.7**	60.6**	43.7**	5576.5**
SCA	166.7**	2.8	944.0**	315.8**	1955.7**	2.6**	74.8**	65.5**	5.9	2.7**	113.1**
VGCAIVSCA	0.24	12.4	9.95	1.46	0.26	6.71	4.17	4.08	18.44	3.67	11.48

^a*** = significant at the 5% and 1% level of probability, respectively. ^bGCA1 = general combining ability (GCA) of female parents; GCA2 = GCA of male parents. VGCA and VSCA = variance due to GCA and SCA.

CIS28-10S, a new indica photoperiod-sensitive, genic male-sterile rice

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CIS28, a B₉F₄ progeny of the cross Caloro/IR28, was bred by Yuan Longping in 1985 as a cyto-nucleoplasm hybrid. We found a spontaneous mutant in 1986, and the indica, photoperiod-sensitive, genic male-sterile germplasm CIS28-10S, one of the derivatives isolated from the spontaneous mutant,

was released in 1989 for use in developing two-line hybrids.

We evaluated CIS28-10S at Xiangtan (28° N) in 1990. Fifty individual plants were spaced at 15 × 20 cm. Plant height, days to 50% flowering, panicle length, grains per panicle, 1,000-grain weight, exerted stigma rate, sterility-transformation and fertility-transformation stages were measured, with CIS28 as the check (see table).

CIS28-10S has very strong ratooning ability, high-yielding agronomic characters, and good grain quality. Floral characters that influence outcrossing rates are also very good.

Performance of CIS28-10S in Xiangtan, China, 1990.

Parameter	CIS28-10S	CIS28 (check)
Sowing time	25 Apr	25 Apr
Days to 50% flowering	15 Jul	25 Jul
Duration (d)	111	121
Plant height (cm)	66	85
Panicle length (cm)	18	17.2
Panicles (no./hill)	14.2	12.1
Grains (no./panicle)	131.5	135.1
1000-grain weight (g)	26	25.8
Exerted stigma (%)	48.3	42.6

The critical stage of sterility transformation is about 15 Jul and fertility transformation 20 Sep under the climatic